

Survey 1

The survey, conducted among 1,682 households as part of a pricing experiment, is detailed in the following paper: *Hofmann, Matthias, and Turid Siebenbrunner. 'A Rich Dataset of Hourly Residential Electricity Consumption Data and Survey Answers from the iFlex Dynamic Pricing Experiment'. Data in Brief 50, No. 109571 (1 October 2023).* <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2023.109571>.

The survey data are published at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/8248802>

This document is published at Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/11580541>

Question q1: In this project, we want to talk with the person in the household who receives the electricity bill - are you the recipient of the electricity bill?

Question q2: What type of electricity contract do you have?

Question q3: Do you buy electricity that is guaranteed to be renewable?

Question q4: What type of building do you live in? Is it a...

Question q5: How large is the home in square meters?

Question q6: Do you own the home?

(IF Question q6 = Yes)

Question q6b1: Do you have a rental unit in the home?

(IF Question q6b1 = Yes)

Question q6b2: Does the rental unit has a separate electricity meter?

(IF Question q6b2 = Yes)

Question q6c: Do several tenants live in the home and share the flat?

Question q7: What year was the building you are answering for built?

Question q8: Has the the home been renovated to reduce energy consumption?

Question q9N1: How is the home heated? Panel heaters

Question q9N2: How is the home heated? Electrical underfloor heating

Question q9N3: How is the home heated? Air-to-air or air-to-water heat pump

Question q9N4: How is the home heated? Geothermal heat

Question q9N5: How is the home heated? Fireplace or wood stove

Question q9N6: How is the home heated? Oil/paraffin/gas/bio oven

Question q9N7: How is the home heated? District heating or other shared solution for heating

Question q9N8: How is the home heated? Other type

(IF Question q9N5 = Main heat source OR Additional heat source)

Question q9d1: In the home you are answering for, how often do you use the fireplace/wood stove? Sometimes, mostly for having it cosy

(IF Question q9N5 = Main heat source OR Additional heat source)

Question q9d2: In the home you are answering for, how often do you use the fireplace/wood stove? Only on the coldest days

(IF Question q9N5 = Main heat source OR Additional heat source)

Question q9d3: In the home you are answering for, how often do you use the fireplace/wood stove? Weekly in winter

(IF Question q9N5 = Main heat source OR Additional heat source)

Question q9d4: In the home you are answering for, how often do you use the fireplace/wood stove? Almost every day in winter

Question q10: What indoor temperature do you usually prefer in the living room when you want to feel comfortable? Temperature:

Question q11: Do you have a lower indoor temperature in rooms that are not used that often?

Question q12: Do you reduce the temperature at night or when no one is home?

Question q13: Do you control the heating?

Question q14: How is the hot water heated in your home?

(IF Question q14 = Own electric water heater)

Question q14b: Do you actively control the electric water heater by switching it on and off or changing the temperature?

Question q15_1: What air ventilation system do you have in your home?

Question q15_2: What air ventilation system do you have in your home?

Question q15_3: What air ventilation system do you have in your home?

Question q15_4: What air ventilation system do you have in your home?

Question q_ekstra_a: Do you actively follow your own electricity consumption?

(IF Question q_ekstra_a = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_b_1: How do you get information about your electricity consumption?
Electricity bill

(IF Question q_ekstra_a = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_b_2: How do you get information about your electricity consumption?
Website (e.g. electricity supplier or others)

(IF Question q_ekstra_a = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_b_3: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? App (e.g. electricity supplier or others)

(IF Question q_ekstra_a = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_b_4: How do you get information about your electricity consumption? Other:

Question q_ekstra_c: Do you follow actively how electricity prices vary?

(IF Question q_ekstra_c = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_d_1: How do you get information about electricity prices? Electricity bill

(IF Question q_ekstra_c = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_d_2: How do you get information about electricity prices? Website (e.g. electricity supplier or others)

(IF Question q_ekstra_c = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_d_3: How do you get information about electricity prices? App (e.g. electricity supplier or others)

(IF Question q_ekstra_c = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_d_4: How do you get information about electricity prices? Media / news

(IF Question q_ekstra_c = Yes)

Question q_ekstra_d_5: How do you get information about electricity prices? Other

Question q16_bil: Do you have a car in your household?

(IF Question q16_bil = Yes)

Question q16_bil_a.1: How many cars do you have in your household? Number:

(IF Question q16_bil = Yes)

Question q16_bil_b: Do you have an electric car or plug-in hybrid in your household?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes)

Question q16.1: How many electric cars or plug-in hybrid cars does your household have?

Number:

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes)

Question q16b6.1: What is the maximum range in kilometers the car can drive electrically?

Car 1:

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes)

Question q16b6.2: What is the maximum range in kilometers the car can drive electrically?

Car 2:

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes)

Question q16b6.3: What is the maximum range in kilometers the car can drive electrically?

Car 3:

(n=0)

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes)

Question q16bN1: Where is the car usually charged? Car 1 (km electric range)

(n=466)

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes)

Question q16bN2: Where is the car usually charged? Car 2 (km electric range)

(n=64)

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes)

Question q16bN3: Where is the car usually charged? Car 3 (km electric range)

(n=0)

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 1)
 Question q16b1_1: How is the car charged at home?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 1)
 Question q16b2_1: How often do you charge your car at home?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 1)
 Question q16b3_1: At what time do you usually charge your car?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 1)

Question q16b4_1: Do you control the charging?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 1)

Question q16b5_1.1: How far, in terms of kilometers, do you usually drive the car before charging it? Kilometers:

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 2)

Question q16b1_2: How is the car charged at home?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 2)

Question q16b2_2: How often do you charge your car at home?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 2)

Question q16b3_2: At what time do you usually charge your car?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 2)

Question q16b4_2: Do you control the charging?

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 2)

Question q16b5_2.1: How far, in terms of kilometers, do you usually drive the car before charging it? Kilometers:

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 3)

Question q16b1_3: How is the car charged at home?

(n=0)

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 3)

Question q16b2_3: How often do you charge your car at home?

(n=0)

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 3)

Question q16b3_3: At what time do you usually charge your car?

(n=0)

|

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 3)

Question q16b4_3: Do you control the charging?

(n=0)

|

(IF Question q16_bil_b = Yes, Car 3)

Question q16b5_3.1: How far, in terms of kilometers, do you usually drive the car before charging it? Kilometers:

(n=0)

|

Question q17: Do you have solar cells?

(IF Question q17 = Yes)

Question q17b.1: How large is the photovoltaic system? Size in kilowatts (kW):

(IF Question q17 = Yes)

Question q17c: Do you have a battery (not an electric car) connected to the photovoltaic system?

Question q18: Inngår strømbruk fra gårdsbruk eller forretningsvirksomhet i samme strømmåleren?

Question q_kjonn: Sex

Question q19: How many people, yourself included, live in your household?

Question q20.1: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 0-1 years

Question q20.2: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 2-5 years

Question q20.3: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 6-15 years

Question q20.4: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 16-22 years

Question q20.5: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 23-29 years

Question q20.6: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 30-39 years

Question q20.7: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 40-49 years

Question q20.8: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 50-66 years

Question q20.9: How old are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... 67 years and older

Question q21: What is the highest completed education in the household?

Question q22: What is the total gross income before taxes of the household?

Question q23: Is someone usually at home during the day on weekdays?

Question q24.1: In what life situation are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... In kindergarten, primary school

Question q24.2: In what life situation are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... Student (high school, college, university)

Question q24.3: In what life situation are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... In part-time job

Question q24.4: In what life situation are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... In full-time job

Question q24.5: In what life situation are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... Unemployed or not in education

Question q24.6: In what life situation are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... Retired

Question q24.7: In what life situation are the household residents? How many of the household's residents are ... Other

Question husstand: Which of the following alternatives describes your household?

(n=1682)

